

A Model for Cybersecurity Risk Management in Digital Transformation (Case Study: An Iranian Bank)

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Abstract

Digital banking is a type of banking based on which the traditional banking business model is transformed. In other words, all products, services, value streams, processes, infrastructures and resources will be redesigned and reengineered based on emerging technologies and based on platform and ecosystem thinking. Today, digital banking is not an opportunity, but a requirement for banks, and if this fact is not accepted, the bank will be practically removed from the competitive market. Due to the expansion of customers' use of the digital banking platform, banking crimes have changed from the traditional field to digital crimes and frauds, which has led to the formation of a new issue of risk in the digital banking industry, called cybersecurity risk. Currently, cybersecurity is considered one of the vital components in banks' risk management, because the lack of proper management of cyber threats causes a wide range of vital damages to organizations, their customers and at the macroeconomic level of a society. Therefore, in this research, we decided to provide a customized model for managing cybersecurity risks in digital banking. The main goal of this research is to identify factors and indicators that are effective in managing cybersecurity risks in the digital banking industry. For this purpose, with a descriptive method based on library studies, we extracted the influential components and indicators and hypotheses of the research, and then with a case study approach and with the help of experts in the field of cybersecurity in one of the largest domestic banks, we examined the model and hypotheses. The main approach used in this research to analyze data and extracted information is the structural equation method. Finally, out of 20 extracted hypotheses, 13 hypotheses were confirmed and their results were presented.

Introduction

In the early 1990s and with the advent of the Internet, eugolana businesses changed to electronic ones, and the electronic age began with the creation of Internet businesses such as ehtInternet or electronic banking. In this era, which is considered the first part of the digitization process, users could perform some simple banking actions such as transferring money and viewing the account balance in the form of electronic and remote banking. With the advancement of technology and the emergence of new technologies such as social networks, artificial intelligence, cloud computing, mobile computing, etc., a new period called the digital age began.

In the digital era, banking concepts also changed from electronic to digital banking. Digital banking has many advanced features, including providing services and executing all transactions through the Internet and applications (T. Nguyen, T. Dang, 2018). Digital Bank is a financial service provider built on a cloud platform. The digital bank is pre-configured and enables commercial banks to provide banking solutions to customers according to their needs, behavior and individual patterns. (Deloitte, 2020) Digital banks in the new era, along with the features of the first generation, have an environment that is completely similar to a physical bank with all the capabilities and the ability to perform all banking operations, including withdrawing from the account, opening a bank deposit, issuing a check, etc., which is equipped with technological capabilities.

Three consecutive stages have been identified in the digitalization process of a bank:

- Development of new channels and products
- Development of technological infrastructure
- The need for deep organizational changes for strategic positioning in the digital environment (Cuesta, 2015)

Elisa Icardi also presented a definition of digital banking in 2022 in the form of the figure 1 (E.Icardi, 2020):

Figure (1) Digital banking

gninioJ this level of transformation in the field of financial and banking operations has been presented many challenges to the banking system, customers and their long-standing laws and regulations; also the creation of the necessary grounds. (M. Roshandel and S. Mollah Ahmad Nalous, 2011) Since digital banking systems operate on the Internet, they are so interest to cyber attackers. The risk of cyber-attack is the highest identified risk in digital banking organizations (RSA Security LLC, 2020).

According to Angel Marcelo et al., cybersecurity is a widely used term that deals with the security of information systems and data. Cybersecurity is defined as the "protection of information assets", by dealing with threats that compromise processed, stored information and interconnected information systems (Angel Marcelo et al, 2020). Besides, Rasan Van Salems states that cybersecurity is different from information security. Information security is the protection of information (which is an asset) from possible damage caused by various threats and various vulnerabilities. Cybersecurity is not necessarily only the protection of cyberspace, but also the protection of those who are in cyberspace and also any assets that can be accessed through cyberspace (Rossouw von Solms, 2013).

Digital banking and cybersecurity are terms used in the digital age to describe technologies, practices and processes that protect data, networks and computer programs from cyber-attacks (Ghelani et al, 2022). For this reason, having effective plans to manage cybersecurity risk in the banking industry is considered much more important than in the past. According to Mark Camillo, erusne tsum snoitutitsni laicnanif they have the right resources in place to manage cybersecurity risks; however, the complexity of contemporary attacks requires a complex response (M. Camillo, 2016).

sknaB must be able to ensure the security of information and data, which requires the use of a comprehensive and native cybersecurity risk management model. If a cybersecurity system is not used to deal with the wide range of threat factors available, these organizations will continue to be the target and victim of fraud groups. Therefore, knowing the latest threat trends will help the organization to create more informed security strategies that improve the cybersecurity risk in banking or financial organizations. Banks can move towards digital banking more confidently by implementing programs that effectively monitor the security situation.

The global banking and financial industry claims that a cyber-attack cost about \$360 billion annually. In recent years, global ransomware attacks have affected financial institutions. (Campbellsville University, 2019) For this purpose, many researchers have been trying to improve the security of cyberspace, and in this way, different solutions have been presented, each of which is analyzed from a different perspective. The risks in cyberspace and the solutions to prevent it have been discussed.

Limna et al. declare the correct presentation of the concept of cybersecurity to related users as a type of security education that can be used to inspire, stimulate, create and rebuild the security skills and prevention practices expected in a specific audience. (Limna et al., 2023)

Anshita Dhout et al. presented a multi-factor authentication model to deal with these attacks. In this smart online banking system model, facial or fingerprint recognition is used for user input and authentication. (A. Dhoot et al, 2020)

In a proposed model, Manivanian fills the gap between users and the bank. This model states that banks can implement their security policies to ensure a safer banking experience for users. On the other hand, users should follow the guidelines provided by the bank to ensure a secure digital banking experience (A. Manivannan, 2020).

In addition, in his research, Lee divided cybersecurity risk into a 4-layers model including cyber ecosystem, cyberinfrastructure layer, cyber risk assessment layer, and cyber performance layer (figure 2) and explained the factors affecting cybersecurity risk management. (I. Lee, 2021)

Figure (2) 4 layers of cybersecurity risk in Lee

In this research, Francisco Zabala and his colleagues examine the threats that may occur in the management of banking services in the process of digitization, as well as the impact on customers and banks, and declares that training personnel in the field of cybersecurity at any time and in any place and after Every stage of training, the official test can help in improving conditions. (F. Zabala et al, 2020)

Abdul Bashir Jabraeel and his colleagues have also defined cybersecurity as the protection of systems connected to the Internet, including hardware, software, and data against cyber-attacks. According to the research conducted by him, cybersecurity threats from the users' point of view are identity theft, impersonation, and account theft, which have been highly influential in the process of accepting digital banking by them. (A.jibril et al, 2020)

However, none of these solutions has been designed and examined in the form of a comprehensive native model based on the banking laws and conditions of the Islamic Republic of Iran. Therefore, in this research, the focus has been on using the data of previous researchers, taking into account the banking laws and regulations of the Islamic Republic of Iran, as well as the existing organizational and public culture in order to use digital banking, in order to be able to create the first native and practical model in the field of risk management. Cybersecurity should be designed according to the internal digital banking culture and laws of our country.

Research Method

Choosing the right research method for research depends on factors such as objectives, the nature of the research, the subject of the research, and the implementation facilities available to the researcher, and the ultimate goal of conducting the research is to achieve correct and easy answers to the research questions. (N.pawar, 2020)

The results obtained from the research are valid and reliable when a suitable method is used in the research, therefore, this research seeks to describe and identify the effective components in increasing cybersecurity risk in the field of digital banking. The research method of this study was descriptive and the nature and method of its implementation is a case study. In this research, both quantitative and qualitative dimensions of the identified components are examined.

For this purpose, to conduct this research, first, the articles published in scientific-research publications, seminars and authentic magazines in the fields of digital banking, cybersecurity and cybersecurity risk management were reviewed, and then based on the information obtained, the influential components and indicators have been identified on the increase of cybersecurity risk in digital banking.

In the next step, to examine the identified components and indicators, the primary statistical population including 10 university professors related to this field and experienced experts in the field of cybersecurity was extracted. Then the initial model along with the identified components and indicators were provided to them to be analyzed and optimized. In the next step, based on the optimal components and indicators that were confirmed by the experts of the first group, a questionnaire was prepared and data collection (samples) was done from the second statistical population, which included 40 experts according to the following indicators.

Four indicators of experts of the second statistical community:

- At least 5 years of work experience related to the research topic
- Familiar with the concepts and functions of digital banking and the existing conditions in the country
- Familiar with cybersecurity risk issues in the digital banking space
- Having at least a master's degree in the research field

Then, based on the final components and indicators, the samples collected from the statistical population and applying the final analysis of the data, the final conceptual model and its assumptions based on structural equations were extracted. In the end, the extracted model was checked based on the confirmatory factor analysis method and the correctness of its performance and related assumptions were also checked.

Research conceptual model

To identify the components that have an impact on the research topic, first, related articles in this field of study and 69 primary components were identified, then based on the aggregation of similar components and applying individual analysis, 11 components were identified and in the first stage, they were provided to primary experts. To reach the final components, five stages of information exchange were carried out between the researcher and the primary experts, and the following edits were obtained in total:

- 4 components were approved without any editing.
- 5 components were edited in different stages of information exchange and renamed for improvement.
- 2 components were removed.
- 2 components were added to the total components during different stages of information exchange.

Finally, the following 11 components were considered for the next steps based on individual analysis and the approval of primary experts.

Independent components:

In this research, national laws, organizational culture, and customer and cyber insurance have been measured as independent components in the model.

Mediating components:

This research evaluated organizational strategies, technology management in the organization, employees, network and program security, information and data security, and correct authentication as mediating components in the model.

Dependent components:

In this research, cybersecurity risk management has been measured as a dependent component in the model.

Research indicators

To identify the indicators of each component, first, related articles in this field were studied and 76 primary indicators were identified, then based on the aggregation of similar indicators and applying individual analysis, 49 indicators were identified and in the first stage, they were provided to primary experts.

To achieve the final indicators, five stages of information exchange were carried out between the researcher and the primary experts, and the following edits were obtained in total:

- In the second stage of information exchange, 6 new indicators were defined and the total number of indicators reached 55.
- In the third stage of exchange, 6 new indicators were added and the total number of indicators reached 61.
- In the fourth stage of exchange, 8 new indicators were added and the total number of indicators reached 69.
- And in the final stage, some indicators were reduced and the total number of indicators reached 61.

Finally, a total of 61 indicators were considered based on individual analysis and the approval of primary experts.(Table 1)

Table (1) Refined components and indices

Component	Indicators
National laws	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1- Supporting cyber defence systems and developing them according to environmental changes 2- Developing policies related to countering cyber attacks 3- Establishing a reference organization regarding tracking and responding to cyber attacks 4- Allocating appropriate funds to prevent cybercrimes 5- Encouraging organizations to share attacks and security events 6- Determining minimum cybersecurity standards and requiring organizations to comply with them
Organizational strategies	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1- Explanation of macro-organizational strategies to reduce the risk of cyber threats 2- Presenting the main organizational policies against cyber threats 3- Determining macro strategies for managing the organization's cyber assets 4- Determining the vision of the organization in cyber risk management 5- Determination of strategic roles and responsibilities in the field of cybersecurity 6- Determining disaster recovery strategies in case of cyber incidents
Technology management in the organization	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1- Using new technologies in predicting and identifying cyber attacks 2- Using advanced technologies in dealing with and managing cyber attacks 3- Establishment of new transparent inspection systems for digital banking transactions 4- Monitoring the current technologies and continuous development and improvement of the systems and technologies used
Organizational Culture	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1- The amount of meritocracy in the organization 2- The level of risk tolerance of personnel 3- Culture of cooperation and teamwork 4- Interest in receiving new training
Employees	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1- Necessary knowledge about threats 2- Spirit and commitment to the organization 3- Job satisfaction 4- Appropriate training in the face of threats
Network and application security	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1- Hardware firewall 2- Software firewall 3- Intrusion detection systems 4- Intranet and Internet network segmentation 5- Prioritizing applications
Information and data security	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1- Using the secure socket layer 2- Encryption (public and private key) 3- Digital signature 4- Scrambling functions 5- Access management other than data and information (confidentiality) 6- Management of change and manipulation of data and information (integrity) 7- Unavailability of service and lack of information exchange (access)
Correct authentication	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1- Using artificial intelligence mechanisms 2- Fingerprint 3- Digital signature 4- Face recognition pattern 5- Hand vascular pattern

		6- IP address tracking 7- Psychological test (making sure that the person is a customer) 8- Security code image 9- password complexity management 10- Changing the password periodically
Cyber insurance		1- Creating a risk transfer mechanism 2- Compensation for the damages caused to the first and third parties 3- Reducing the costs of internet attacks 4- Increasing the sense of security and smoothing the path to the realization of digital banking
Cybersecurity management	risk	1- Improve resilience 2- Improving efficiency 3- Improving effectiveness 4- Improving reliability 5- Maintaining assets (information, hardware, etc.)

Then, the conceptual model of the research was created in the SmartPLS software based on the identified components and indicators. Figure 3 shows the conceptual model.

Figure (3) conceptual model based on refined components and indicators

Finally, 20 hypotheses based on the drawn conceptual model were identified as follows:

- 1- Cyber insurance has an impact on cybersecurity risk management.
- 2- Organizational strategies have an impact on cybersecurity risk management.
- 3- Technology leadership in the organization has an impact on cybersecurity risk management.

- 4- Network and program security has an impact on cybersecurity risk management.
- 5- Information and data security has an impact on cybersecurity risk management.
- 6- Correct authentication has an impact on cybersecurity risk management.
- 7- The customer has an impact on cybersecurity risk management.
- 8- Employees have an impact on cybersecurity risk management.
- 9- National laws have an impact on organizational strategies.
- 10- Organizational strategies have an effect on the management of technology in the organization.
- 11- Technology management in the organization has an impact on the security of the network and programs.
- 12- Technology management in the organization has an impact on the security of information and data.
- 13- Technology management in the organization has an impact on correct authentication.
- 14- Organizational culture has an impact on employees.
- 15- Employees have a mediating role in the relationship between organizational culture and cybersecurity risk management.
- 16- Organizational strategies have a mediating role in the relationship between national laws and cybersecurity risk management.
- 17- Technology leadership in the organization has a mediating role in the relationship between organizational strategies and cybersecurity risk management.
- 18- Network and program security evah a mediating role in the relationship between technology management in the organization and cybersecurity risk management.
- 19- Information and data security has a mediating role in the relationship between technology management in the organization and cybersecurity risk management.
- 20- Correct authentication has a mediating role in the relationship between technology management in the organization and cybersecurity risk management

Findings

Data analysis is one of the most important parts of research. At this stage, based on statistical calculations, the accuracy and validity of the questionnaire and model will be examined, and at the end, the identified hypotheses will be analyzed to confirm or reject them.

Validity and reliability of the questionnaire:

The tools used to collect data must have validity or credibility in the first stage and reliability or trust in the second stage. Therefore, in this research, the face and content validity and reliability of the questionnaire have been investigated using statistical methods.

Face validity:

In this research, to estimate the face validity, the questionnaire was distributed among the primary experts and the experts were asked to express their opinions about the appropriateness of the questions in the questionnaire to measure the target index as well as the existing ambiguities while answering the questions. Then, experts' correction comments were applied to the questionnaire.

Content validity:

To check the content validity of the questionnaire questions, the Lavshe coefficient was used. This method measures the degree of essentiality and approval of a particular item among experts or evaluators. This measurement is calculated through the following formula:

$$CVR = \frac{(ne - \frac{N}{2})}{\frac{N}{2}}$$

CVR is the content validity ratio, ne is the number of experts or evaluators who consider the topic to be essential or useful, and N is the total number of experts or evaluators. Content validity for questionnaire indicators was calculated based on the opinions of 10 experts (primary statistical population). Based on the number of 10 experts, the minimum CVR of the content validity of the questionnaire for each question should be above 0.62 to confirm the content validity of the question. According to the calculations, all identified questions have appropriate content validity and the validity of the questionnaire was confirmed.

Convergence validity of components

Convergence validity criterion which is displayed with the abbreviation AVE and shows the degree of correlation of a component with the indicators of the same component. This criterion is calculated based on the average extracted variance of research components and the optimal limit for each component should be more than 0.5. (James B. Grace, 2010) according to the calculation of the average values of the extracted variance of all 11 components of the model, they were at the optimal level (more than 0.5).

Divergence validity of the components

To check the validity of the divergence of the components, the Fornell-Larker matrix was used. The rows and columns of this matrix represent 11 research components and their values represent the relationship of a component with its indicators and also with other components. Table 2 shows the validity check matrix of model divergence. The houses of this matrix contain the squared values of the correlation coefficients between the components (coefficients at the bottom of the triangle) and the square root of the average extracted variance values for each component (on the main diameter). The main diameter is larger than the lower values of the triangle of the matrix, therefore, the validity of the divergence of the model is confirmed by Fornell and Larcker's method. (Table2)

Table (2) checks the validity of the divergence of the research components with the method of Fornell and Larker

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
National laws	0/730										
Organizational strategies	0/124	0/707									
Technology management in the organization	0/142	0/509	0/767								
Organizational Culture	0/156	0/305	0/354	0/744							
Employees	0/134	0/110	0/333	0/111	0/772						
Network and application security	0/112	0/105	0/409	0/175	0/412	0/714					
Information and data security	0/152	0/444	0/117	0/222	0/227	0/324	0/724				
Correct authentication	0/130	0/305	0/450	0/147	0/440	0/258	0/344	0/730			
Customer	0/174	0/110	0/441	0/484	0/478	0/245	0/356	0/244	0/719		
Cyber insurance	0/356	0/105	0/370	0/414	0/204	0/415	0/344	0/322	0/421	0/772	
Cybersecurity risk management	0/089	0/147	0/404	0/222	0/541	0/448	0/399	0/120	0/289	0/241	0/788

Reliability of the questionnaire:

The reliability of a measurement tool states that if we use the same measurement tool at several different times and in the same statistical population, there should not be a significant difference in the results. In other words, this feature states how much the measurement tool includes similar results under the same conditions. In this research, the reliability of the used questionnaire is evaluated with the help of Cronbach's alpha.

If the calculated reliability coefficient is close to 0.1, it shows that the reliability of the questionnaire is higher. Also, a coefficient less than 0.60 is considered weak, values between 0.60 and 0.70 are acceptable, and values greater than 0.80 are considered good, and it is clear that the closer the obtained coefficient is to 1, Reliability is more desirable (Mohammad Reza Hafez Nia, 2011).

$$r_{\alpha} = \frac{J}{J-1} \left(1 - \frac{\sum S_j^2}{S^2}\right)$$

According to the calculations, the produced questionnaire had adequate reliability in such a way that 9 out of 11 identified components have Cronbach's alpha above 80. The other two items are 0.763 and 0.768. Therefore, the reliability of the questionnaire is confirmed.

Normality of the distribution of research components

Kolmogorov-Smirnovtest is used to check the claim made about the data distribution of a quantitative component. The statistical assumptions related to normal distribution are presented as follows:

- H_0 : The components have a normal distribution.
- H_1 : The components do not have a normal distribution.

The results of the test conducted in SPSS software showed that the components of national laws, technology management in the organization, and customer and cybersecurity risk management have a significant level greater than 0.05 and the claim of normal distribution of these components is accepted, but in For other components, the significance level is less than 0.05, so the distribution of these components is not normal. Because some components do not have a normal distribution, PLS software, in which the normality of the distribution of the components is not required, was used to fit the model.

Examining the fit of the structural model

In this section, the appropriateness of the fit of the structural model of the research is investigated using four criteria: coefficient of determination (R^2), Stone-Geisser coefficient (Q^2), redundancy criterion and the significant coefficients of each of the questions attributed to the research components (t-value) Is.

Coefficient of determination (R^2):

The coefficient of determination is a measure that shows the effect of an exogenous component on an endogenous component. Three values of 0.19, 0.33 and 0.67 have been introduced as criteria for weak, medium and strong values of the coefficient of determination. (James B. Grace, 2010)

Stone-Geisser coefficient (Q^2):

This measure shows the predictive power of the model. Regarding the severity of the predictive power of the model regarding the endogenous components, three values of 0.02 (weak), 0.15 (moderate) and 0.35 (strong) have been determined. (Table 3)

Table (3) Determination coefficients and Stone-Geisser

Endogenous components of the model	Aston-Geisser(Q^2) coefficient	The coefficient of determination (R^2)
Organizational strategies	0/309	0.667
Technology management in the organization	0/330	0/563
Employees	0/282	0/483
Network and application security	0/227	0/527
Information and data security	0/303	0/053
Correct authentication	0/301	0/639
Cybersecurity risk management	0/162	0/668
Average	0/273	0/514

Redundancy criterion

This criterion is the result of multiplying the common values of the endogenous component by the value of the coefficient of determination related to that component and indicates the amount of variability of the indicators of an endogenous component that is affected by one or more exogenous components. The higher the Redundancy value, the more suitable the structural part of the model is in a study (RSA Security LLC, 2020).

Table 4 shows the average value of redundancy for 7 endogenous components of the model. It can be seen that the average of the coefficients is within the desired and acceptable level (0.286). Therefore, the model has a good fit.

Table (4) Redundancy criterion

Endogenous components	The coefficient of (R^2)determination	communality	Redundancy	\overline{Red}
Organizational strategies	0/667	0/501	0/334	0/286
Technology management in the organization	0/563	0/589	0/331	
Employees	0/483	0/596	0/287	
Network and application security	0/527	0/511	0/269	
Information and data security	0/053	0/525	0/027	
Correct authentication	0/639	0/534	0/341	
Cybersecurity risk management	0/668	0/621	0/414	

Significant examination of the questions of each component

Another criterion that has been used to show the suitability of the structural model used in this research is the t-statistic of each of the questions attributed to the research components. At the error level of 0.05, if the t-statistic is more than 1.96, it indicates the desirability of the questions and the overall fit of the structural model. (James B. Grace, 2010) If the t coefficient is lower than this number, that question should be removed. According to the calculations made for all questions, the T-statistic is more than 1.96.

GOF criterion

The fit of the general structural equation model can be checked with only one GOF criterion. Three values of 0.01, 0.25 and 0.36 have been introduced as weak, medium and strong values for GOF. (James B. Grace, 2010)

$$GOF = \sqrt{R^2} \times \sqrt{\text{communalities}}$$

Table 5 shows the GOF value for the research model. It can be seen that the coefficient is within the desired and acceptable level (0.535). Therefore, the model has a good overall fit.

Table (5) GOF value of the model

Model components	communalities	The coefficient of determination (R^2)	$\sqrt{\text{communalities}}$	$\sqrt{R^2}$	GOF
National laws	0/596				
Organizational Culture	0/501				
Customer	0/517				
Cyber insurance	0/596				
Organizational strategies	0/501	0/667			
Organizational strategies	0/589	0/563			
Employees	0/596	0/483			
Network and application security	0/511	0/527			
Information and data security	0/525	0/053			
Correct authentication	0/534	0/639			
Cybersecurity risk management	0/621	0/668			
			0/557	0/514	0/535

Examining research hypotheses

After ensuring the fit of the measurement model, the fit of the structural model and the desirability of the overall research model, we can now deal with the relationships between the components and test the hypotheses under the conceptual model.

For this purpose, first, the path coefficient values will be calculated for the conceptual model. Path coefficients are between -1 and 1. If a path is close to 1, it indicates a direct and significant relationship between the components, and if the coefficient is close to -1, it indicates an inverse and significant relationship between the two components. If the value is 0, there is no significant relationship between the two components. Figure 4 shows the research model along with its path coefficients.

Figure (4) conceptual model with path coefficients

Since it is not possible to confirm or reject a hypothesis by just calculating and displaying the path coefficients, therefore, the value of the T-Value test statistic has been used to show the significance of the path coefficient and the status of confirming or rejecting the presented hypotheses. As mentioned earlier, the value (t-value) is a critical number and if it is more than 1.96, it indicates the significance of the relationship at the confidence level of 95% and confirms the research hypothesis. (James B. Grace, 2010)

Figure 5 shows the research model that includes the test statistic value (t-Value). Hypotheses based on relationships with a weight above 1.96, which include 13 hypotheses, have been approved.

Figure (5) conceptual model with a t statistic

In the end, the 20 hypotheses extracted based on the generated conceptual model are presented separately in Table 5 along with their confirmation or rejection status.

Table (5) of the final state of research assumptions

assumptions	Path coefficient	t-Value	The result of the hypothesis test
The impact of cyber insurance on cybersecurity risk management	0/139	1/970	Confirmed(%95)
The impact of organizational strategies on cybersecurity Risk management	0/889	30/253	Confirmed(%99)
The impact of technology leadership in the organization on cybersecurity risk management	0/083	2/384	Confirmed(%95)
Impact of network security and Applications on cybersecurity risk management	-0/015	0/648	Rejected
The impact of information and data security on cybersecurity risk management	0/075	0/958	Rejected
The impact of correct authentication on cybersecurity risk management	0/022	0/465	Rejected
Customer Impact on cybersecurity risk management	0/125	4/061	Confirmed(%99)
The impact of employees on cybersecurity risk management	0/051	2/141	Confirmed(%95)
The impact of national laws on organizational strategies	0/817	65/345	Confirmed(%99)
The effect of organizational strategies on the management of technology in the organization	0/751	37/294	Confirmed(%99)
The impact of technology leadership in the	0/726	41/403	Confirmed(%99)

organization on the security of the network and programs			
The impact of technology management in the organization on information and data security	0/232	3/615	Confirmed(%99)
The impact of technology leadership in the organization on correct authentication	0/800	110/025	Confirmed(%99)
The Impact of organizational culture on Employees	0/695	45/765	Confirmed(%99)
The impact of employees' mediating role on the relationship between organizational culture and cybersecurity risk management	0/035	1/125	Rejected
The effect of the mediating role of organizational strategies in the relationship between national laws and cybersecurity risk management	0/726	40/360	Confirmed(%99)
The effect of mediating the role of technology management in the organization in the relationship between organizational strategies and cybersecurity risk management	0/062	2/152	Confirmed(%95)
The effect of mediating the role of network security and programs in the relationship between technology management in the organization and cybersecurity risk management	-0/010	0/660	Rejected
The effect of the mediating role of information and data security in the relationship between technology management in the organization and cybersecurity risk management	0/017	0/715	Rejected
The effect of the mediating role of correct authentication in the relationship between technology management in the organization and cybersecurity risk management	0/018	0/729	Rejected

Discussion and Conclusion

In this research, the question "What is the appropriate model for cybersecurity risk management in digital banking?" has been discussed and an effort has been made to provide a practical conceptual model approved by the experts to manage and improve the conditions of cybersecurity risk in digital banking. For this purpose, using the descriptive approach in the studied bank, the influential components and indicators were identified with the help of experts, and then the assumptions and conceptual model obtained were evaluated using the structural equation method.

In this research, a total of 20 hypotheses were presented, according to Table 5 and based on the calculation of path coefficient and t statistic for each hypothesis, 13 hypotheses were confirmed and 7 hypotheses were rejected.

- 1-Regarding the result obtained and the positive coefficient of the relationship, it can be said that cyber insurance has a direct relationship with cybersecurity risk management, and due to the presence of the t-statistic greater than 1.96, this relationship has been confirmed.
- 2-Regarding the result obtained and the positive coefficient of the relationship, it can be said that organizational strategies have a direct relationship with cybersecurity risk management, and due to the presence of the t-statistic greater than 1.96, this relationship has been confirmed.
- 3-Regarding the result obtained and the positive coefficient of the relationship, it can be said that technology management in the organization had a direct relationship with cybersecurity risk management, and due to the existence of a t-statistic greater than 1.96, this relationship has been confirmed.
- 4-Regarding the result obtained and the negative coefficient of the relationship, it can be said that the security of the network and programs in the organization had an inverse relationship with the cybersecurity risk management, but due to the presence of the t-statistic smaller than 1.96, the hypothesis has been rejected and therefore the relationship is not valid.
- 5-Regarding the result obtained and the positive coefficient of the relationship, it can be said that information and data security in the organization has a direct relationship with cybersecurity risk

- management, but due to the presence of the t-statistic smaller than 1.96, the hypothesis has been rejected and therefore the relationship is not valid.
- 6-Regarding the result obtained and the positive coefficient of the relationship, it can be said that proper authentication in the organization has a direct relationship with cybersecurity risk management, but due to the existence of the t-statistic smaller than 1.96, the hypothesis has been rejected and therefore the relationship is not valid.
 - 7-Regarding the result obtained and the positive coefficient of the relationship, it can be said that the customer has had a direct relationship with cybersecurity risk management and due to the presence of the t-statistic greater than 1.96, this relationship has been confirmed.
 - 8-Regarding the result obtained and the positive coefficient of the relationship, it can be said that employees in the organization had a direct relationship with cybersecurity risk management, and due to the presence of the t-statistic greater than 1.96, this relationship has been confirmed.
 - 9-Regarding the result obtained and the positive coefficient of the relationship, it can be said that national laws have a direct relationship with organizational strategies, and due to the presence of the t-statistic greater than 1.96, this relationship has been confirmed.
 - 10-Regarding the result obtained and the positive coefficient of the relationship, it can be said that organizational strategies have a direct relationship with technology management in the organization, and due to the presence of the t-statistic greater than 1.96, this relationship has been confirmed.
 - 11-Regarding the result obtained and the positive coefficient of the relationship, it can be said that the management of technology in the organization has a direct relationship with the security of the network and programs, and due to the presence of the t-statistic greater than 1.96, this relationship has been confirmed.
 - 12-Regarding the result obtained and the positive coefficient of the relationship, it can be said that the management of technology in the organization had a direct relationship with the security of information and data, and due to the presence of the t-statistic greater than 1.96, this relationship has been confirmed.
 - 13-Regarding the result obtained and the positive coefficient of the relationship, it can be said that the management of technology in the organization had a direct relationship with the correct authentication, and due to the presence of the t-statistic greater than 1.96, this relationship has been confirmed.
 - 14-Regarding the result obtained and the positive coefficient of the relationship, it can be said that the organizational culture had a direct relationship with the employees, and due to the presence of the t-statistic greater than 1.96, this relationship has been confirmed.
 - 15-Regarding the result obtained and the positive coefficient of the relationship, it can be said that employees in the organization had a direct mediating role in the relationship between organizational culture and cybersecurity risk management, but due to the presence of the t-statistic smaller than 1.96, the hypothesis has been rejected. Therefore the relationship is not valid.
 - 16-Regarding the result obtained and the positive coefficient of the relationship, it can be said that employees in the organization had a direct mediating role in the relationship between organizational culture and cybersecurity risk management, and due to the existence of a t-statistic greater than 1.96, this relationship has been confirmed.
 - 17-Regarding the result obtained and the positive coefficient of the relationship, it can be said that technology management in the organization has a direct mediating role in organizational strategies and cybersecurity risk management, and due to the presence of the t-statistic, this relationship is greater than 1.96, this relationship has been confirmed.
 - 18-Regarding the result obtained and the negative coefficient of the relationship, it can be said that the security of the network and programs in the organization has played an inverse mediating role in the relationship between technology management in the organization and cybersecurity risk management, but due to the existence of a smaller t-statistic From 1.96, the hypothesis has been rejected and therefore the relationship is not valid.
 - 19-Regarding the result obtained and the positive coefficient of the relationship, it can be said that information and data security in the organization had a direct mediating role in the relationship between technology management in the organization and cybersecurity risk management, but due to the existence of a smaller t-statistic From 1.96, the hypothesis has been rejected and therefore the relationship is not valid.
 - 20-Regarding the result obtained and the positive coefficient of the relationship, it can be said that the correct authentication in the organization had a direct mediating role in the relationship between technology management in the organization and cybersecurity risk management, but due to the existence of the t-statistic smaller than 1.96, the hypothesis has been rejected and therefore the relationship is not valid.

Suggestions for future research:

According to the findings of the research, suggestions are presented to future researchers as follows:

- 1- It is suggested that demographic factors such as gender, age, and education level of people are added to the moderating factors in the conceptual model and the role of these components in decreasing and increasing relationships should be determined.
- 2- Research similar to this research should be conducted with other statistical communities, such as state banks or financial institutions so that a comprehensive model can be achieved at the country level.
- 3- Implementing the presented model and checking the model in the operational environment can provide appropriate practical and field results of the accuracy of the model's performance.
- 4- It is suggested that in future research, the researchers prioritize and accurately weigh the components and their indicators and examine the effects of each component according to its priority.

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